

E-Book MARC Records for Integration into Koha LMS: Practical Experience at St. Xavier's College Central Library, Kolkata

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ABSTRACT

Modern technology has brought electronic books (e-books) to the readers which are now very useful due to space constraint as well as budgetary constraint. So, now a days, academic libraries gradually prefer e-books to print books for academic and research purposes. St. Xavier's College Central Library is also following the same path by acquiring e-books from several vendors. The e-book vendors provide MARC records either through their official website or as per our requirement, which can be easily downloadable for integration into its Koha LMS. This paper will highlight the step by step integration process of bulk MARC records of e-books into Koha LMS. It also discusses the benefits arising out of this integration process, such as single window search facility i.e. printed books as well as e-books in the same user interface and it also discusses the types of problems faced during the integration process and their way-out to overcome.

Keywords: marc records, e-book, marcedit, koha lms

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1971 it came into existence of e-book era. E-books are very popular due to its various advantages. Simultaneous access (24x7) within the campus as well as outside the campus of the educational institution is a reality now which is void in case of printed books. Besides these can be downloaded, organised and shelved in a virtual reality for posterity. So is the reason for its popularity. Now e-book MARC records are easily downloadable not only for integration into any MARC enabled library management software (LMS) but also very convenient for bibliographic information exchange among various entities. Central Library of St. Xavier's College has been procuring e-books for its readers. It integrates MARC data into its Koha LMS so that readers can conveniently get the information regarding the collection strength and its item wise distribution. The present paper discusses the integration of MARC bibliographic data of e-books procured by St. Xavier's College Central Library, Kolkata, West Bengal into its library management software Koha and the issues confronted during the integration process and their respective solutions.

II. E-BOOK COLLECTION AT ST. XAVIER'S COLLEGE CENTRAL LIBRARY, KOLKATA

This integration process of MARC records into Koha LMS is particularly applied only for the e-books purchased directly from the vendors based on "pick and choose" model. The library purchased 85 titles from Pearson (broad subject areas include Mathematics, Sociology, Political Science, Chemistry, Computer Science, and Physics), 5 titles on Human Rights from Gale Cengage Learning Online, 104 titles (mainly on Economics, Physics, Biotechnology, Mathematics, Commerce, Sociology) from Oxford Scholarship Online. Perpetual access to these e-books is IP based.

III. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Objectives of the study are to create awareness on usefulness of procuring e-books and to show the integration process of e-book MARC records for library management software Koha in resource dissemination for an academic library viz. St. Xavier's College Central Library, Kolkata, West Bengal, India and also mention the issues faced by the entity while integration

process carried out and the advantages accrued after integration process based on the practical experience. E-Book vendors those are not able to provide MARC records are not taken into consideration for the study.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. F. Adrakatti, S. S. Kalyani and K. R. Mulla (2015) did integration work for Library Management Software (LMS) Koha with the MARC records of e-book collection of an institute. They stressed on the integration process step by step and discussed the issues coming out during the integration process.

The authors of the present paper tried to do it for their academic library and recorded the experience gained during their work in this paper.

V. METHODOLOGY

It is a field based activity where the library software Koha is updated with e-book MARC records for dissemination of library resources' metadata. Screenshots of respective steps and their results are furnished in the present paper.

VI. INTEGRATION PROCESS: THE PRACTICAL APPROACH OF INTEGRATING E-BOOK MARC RECORDS INTO KOHA LMS

6.1 Download MARC Records from Publisher Website

The publisher or aggregator like Sage, Oxford will have a provision to download freely up to date MARC file [Fig: 1] from their respective official website. Some of the publishers also provide MARC file based on library administrator's request.

Figure 1: Sample view of E-Book MARC Records downloaded from Oxford.com

6.2 Customizing Records using MarcEdit Software

The downloaded MARC record file is saved in .mrk extension. The records contain only the basic fields and tags. For integrating marc records into Koha, it is required to compile the MARC records into binary MARC file with .mrc extension. The records need to be customized using MarcEdit software under MARC Tools [Fig: 2]. Add 942\$c tag for ebook type and then add 952 tag for respective branch location, price and item type information etc. After successful compilation the file will be saved with .mrc extension.

Figure 2: Screenshot for Customizing MARC Records using MARCEdit Software

6.3 Integration of DDC or LC Call Number from OCLC:

OCLC's Classify Web Service [Fig: 3] is also integrated with the MarcEdit software. Using this facility the system will automatically import Dewey Decimal or LC call number for all the records or selected records. We can also integrate Subject Headings with the help of FAST heading.

Figure 3: Snapshot of Integration of DDC or LC Call Number from OCLC's Classify Web Service

6.4 Staged MARC Record Management

This option is used for applying different new and action matching rules i.e. if matching record found, if no match found etc, for importing MARC record into koha database. The status report will show the completed import records along with number of records staged, not staged, updated, ignored and number of items added into catalogue.

Figure 4

6.5 Records Display in Staff and User Interface

Now rebuild zebra indexing using command line prompt in the koha terminal. After successful integration of eBook marc records in to the koha, the imported eBook records can be searched from both user OPAC interface and the staff interface [Fig:5, Fig:6].

Figure 5: Snapshot of search result display of eBook records in the koha user interface with cover page

Figure 6: Snapshot of search result display of eBook records in the koha staff interface with cover page

6.6 Trouble Shooting

Issue No: 1: Failed to upload the MARC file:

In the koha admin interface under the tools there is an option stage MARC records for import, but after importing the file the MARC staging result shows 0 items records found and staged [Fig:7, 8].

Solution: From Koha user manual we find out the solution of the error. The error was in the imported marc file format. We had imported the customized marc file i.e. .mrk extension without marc compilation i.e. .mrc extension.

Figure: 7

Issue No: 2: Removing the bulk bibliographic records from the koha database:

It is very difficult and time-consuming process of deleting the bibliographic records one by one, if the records number is more than thousands together [Fig:8].

Solution: In the koha admin, interface under the tools option, there is an option of bulk record deletion. To use this facility administrator should know exact bibliographic record number of the e-book which one he wants to remove. Another way to remove the records, undo import from Manage staged MARC records by clicking on the uploaded file name. This happens in case of limited period subscription-based e-book purchase model. However, in case of perpetual access-based model this type of problem never arises.

#	File name	Comments	Type	Status	Staged	# Records	# Items	Action
24	oso_biology_2019.mrk		Bibliographic	Staged	2019-11-20 15:37:59	0	0	Clean
23	oso_biology_2019.mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2019-11-20 15:04:43	4	0	Clean
21	FASTfile.mrc	Uniform title	Authority	Staged	2019-02-15 16:42:46	68792	0	Clean
10	MarcRecords.mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2016-03-09 17:44:44	27	0	Clean
7	PG-PHY_sougata_16-12-13.mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2014-06-25 06:37:35	33	134 (Create label batch)	Clean
6	REPORTS(rectified).mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2014-06-25 06:36:57	207	229 (Create label batch)	Clean
5	CD-DVD(rectified).mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2014-06-25 06:34:33	819	1815 (Create label batch)	Clean
4	FINAL KOHA TRANSFER-21.06.14.mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2014-06-25 06:03:04	40139	58509 (Create label batch)	Clean
3	BOOKS-BED(JHUNU)26.06.14.mrc		Bibliographic	Imported	2014-06-25 05:27:23	5390	7766 (Create label batch)	Clean
1	BOOKS-BED(JHUNU)12.03.14.mrc		Bibliographic	Reverted	2014-03-15 01:26:42	5390	7766 (Create label batch)	Clean

Figure: 8

VII. ADVANTAGES

The advantages of integration of e-book MARC records in the Koha LMS are as follows:

- OPAC interface acts as a single window search interface for both e-books and printed books
- Increased effective usage of e-books for the study and research purpose
- Avoiding searching multiple publishers' website
- Save time of the users i.e. fulfil 4th Law of Library Science
- Increased awareness and promotion of purchased e-books
- Copy cataloguing facility saves the time of the cataloguer and maintains standard MARC format in the bibliographic database.

VIII. CONCLUSION

E-books are becoming more important due to their several advantages. So, integration of e-book marc records is adding value to the existing bibliographic database of the library collection. E-books can be accessed based either on IP address or by using user Id Password. In the former case users are deprived of accessing entire content of the e-books, user can view only the bibliographic details of the e-book when users are outside the campus i.e. outside the IP address range. However, in the latter case users can get benefit of this integration process by viewing not only the bibliographic details but also the entire content of the e-book. The integration process saves the time of the cataloguer only by importing bulk MARC records from e-book vendors and exporting the same into Koha LMS and at the same time it saves the time of the readers by providing single window search facility as they do not need to browse the individual websites of the e-book vendors.

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